

Exploration of In Vitro Anti-Cancer Activity of Ethanolic Extract of Leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* by BSL (Brine Shrimp Lethality) Method

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to focus on the cytotoxicity by brine shrimp bioassay, which is simple, reliable and convenient method for assessment of bio-activity of folklore Indian medicinal plant i.e. leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* belong to the family *Araceae*. Brine shrimp Lethality bioassay method was established for the present study and the cytotoxicity was reported in term of lethality concentration (LC₅₀). The shrimps were hatched and active shrimps were collected and used for the assay, 10 active shrimps were added to the 2.5 ml dilute test solution and the surviving (larvae) shrimps were counted after 24 hours and lethality concentration (LC₅₀) was assessed. In the present study, alcoholic extract of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* exhibited potent brine shrimp lethality (LC₅₀) as 10,20,30,40 and 50µg/ml respectively. Preliminary phytochemical screening showed the existence of alkaloids, flavonoids, Saponins, carbohydrates, in alcoholic extract of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* pharmacological screening also confirms that the alcoholic extract of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* at 50µg/ml has more potent anti-cancer activity by BSL method. The study further concludes that, this anti-cancer activity may be due to the presence of active phytoconstituents present in the plant and extends the support for further research.

Keywords: Anti-Cancer; *Colocasia Esculenta*; Brine Shrimp Lethality; Ethanolic Extract.

1. INTRODUCTION:

In 2018, there were 9.6 million cancer-related deaths and 18.1 million new instances of the disease. With 36 distinct forms, the most common cancers to affect males are colorectal, liver, lung, prostate, and stomach cancers; the most common cancers to affect women are breast, cervical, colorectal, lung, and thyroid cancers¹. Research on cancer treatment has emerged as a completely new field. Both very contemporary and old methods are used to treat cancer. Cancer is treated using a range of methods, such as radiation therapy, chemotherapy, and surgery. They all have certain drawbacks, albeit². The usage of traditional chemicals has toxicities and adverse effects³. However, because the issue still exists, novel strategies are required for disease control, particularly in light of the shortcomings of traditional chemotherapeutic methods. Thus, in order to reduce the number of people dying from cancer, new approaches to its prevention and treatment are required. Herbal therapy has developed into a relatively accessible, non-toxic, and safe source of substances that treat cancer. Because of a variety of properties, herbs are thought to counteract the effects of diseases in the body⁴. For example, of the various medicinal plants with anticancer characteristics, *Phaleriamacrocarpa* (local name: Mahkotadewa) and *Fagoniaindica* (local name: Dhamasa) have long been employed for their active components' anticancer effects^{5,6}. The plant material's metabolites are employed to cause cancer cells to undergo apoptosis. Purified from *P. macrocarpa* fruit extract, gallic acid is the

active ingredient that has been shown to play a role in inducing apoptosis in lung cancer, leukaemia, and colon adenocarcinoma cell lines^{7,8}. It is a polyhydroxy phenolic chemical that is found in many natural foods, such as green tea, vegetables, bananas, grapes, and strawberries⁹. It is also a naturally occurring antioxidant. Additionally, it is essential in halting the growth of cancer and the transformation of malignancy¹⁰.

Similar to this, additional substances derived from different plants, such as camptothecin, podophyllotoxin, and vinca alkaloids, are employed in the treatment of cancer. The usage of herbs was long neglected due to the development of industrial medicine and the business sector¹¹. New techniques have made it easier to deal with natural substances, and the pharmaceutical industry is becoming more interested in using these natural ingredients^{12,13}. The World Health Organization estimates that 80% of people worldwide still receive treatment through conventional means¹⁴.

The current field of biomolecular science has made significant advancements in understanding the impacts and activities of herbs on a variety of targets, including their anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer characteristics. The benefits of such herbal therapy against many cancer kinds have also been recognized, as knowledge of their effects grows. Hepatocellular carcinomas (HCC), for example, are thought to be the fifth most prevalent cancer worldwide and are becoming more common^{15,16}. Numerous research on the prevention and treatment of HCC using herbal medicine have demonstrated that some herb components may have an impact on the initiation, development, and progression of HCC^{17,18}.

It is a misconception that herbal substances have no safety concerns or adverse effects, even if they are classified as medications. There are hundreds of plant species that are harmful to human health. Similarly, several chemicals found in otherwise amiable plants also have harmful properties. Tests have demonstrated that even anticancer herbs have harmful effects¹⁹. In the United States of America, herbal supplements are governed under the "dietary supplement health and education act." This study focuses on the mechanisms of action of several highly significant anticancer plants, the research around these mechanisms, the active chemicals they contain, and the rules that govern them²⁰.

The Araceae family includes the plant *Colocasia esculenta*, whose leaves are popularly referred to as taro. It is a tropical plant that was initially found in South-east Asia, near the Bay of Bengal. This herb, which is perennial, has thick, subterranean tuberous stems. The amazing starch and fiber found in *Colocasia esculenta* contribute to a host of health advantages, including lower blood sugar, better skin care, and a decrease in obesity. Since there hasn't been any significant research on *Colocasia esculenta's* anticancer potential, our study concentrated on assessing the plant's cytotoxic activity to bolster the plant's traditional medicinal uses.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD:

2.1 Collection and authentication of plant material:

The plant were procured from the farm and authentication by Dr. R.F. Suryvunashi, HOD Botany, Dr. Ganpatrao Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya Sangola, Solapur, India. leaves were dried at room temprature in shade & crushed to coarse powder by mechanical grinder. This coarse powder kept in

airtight plastic bag & used it for further study.

2.2 Morphological characters:

Morphological characteristics includes the macroscopic study related to the color, odor, taste and consistency of the leaves of *Colocasia esculenta*.

2.3 Microscopic characters:

To take a transverse section of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* before that we first clear the piece of the leaf (middle part) by boiled the leaf in chloral hydrate solution or alternatively with chlorinated soda. Then peel out upper and lower epidermis separately by means of forceps keep it on slide and mount in glycerin water, then place the slide with the cleared leaf (epidermis) on the stage trace the epidermal cell and calculated the stomatal number, stomatal index, vein-islet number, vein termination number.

Calcium oxalate is a common biomineral in plants, occurring as crystals of various shapes. it is avital component of the load-bearing network, powder microscopy of leaves powder of *Colocasia esculenta* shows the presence of lignified cell, mucilage, calcium oxalate crystals. This is used for the standardization of the drug.

2.4 Proximate analysis:

Proximate analysis includes the parameters – total ash value, water soluble ash value, acid insoluble ash value, water soluble extractive value and alcohol soluble extractive value. This proximate analysis helps to identify the adulteration and gives the information about the quality of the sample. Ash value is useful in determination the purity of the sample.

2.5 Sample preparation for extraction:

Dried *Colocasia esculenta* was size reduced to mesh size # 80 and used phytochemical analysis 30gm of coarse powder extracted with ethanol using Soxhlet apparatus for 8 hours & distilled waters by maceration for 24 hours respectively, then filtered to yield the extracts. The dried ethanolic of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* were used for evaluation.

2.6 Qualitative phytochemical analysis:

Phytochemical tests are performed to detect the presence of secondary metabolites (phytoconstituents) in the plant materials & carried out by standard method²¹.

2.7 Assay for anti-cancer activity (Brine Shrimp Lethality Bioassay)²²

2.7.1 Hatching of Brine Shrimp:

38 gm of sea salt (without iodine) & 0.006 mg yeast was weighted & dissolved in one litre distilled water & filter off to get clear solution. *Artemia Salina* Shrimp (Brine Shrimp egg) were added to one side of sea water & then covered the tank 48 hours allowed to hatch the shrimp constant oxygen supply was carried throughout the hatching time under dark area.

2.7.2 Preparation of stock & test solution:

1 gm of ethanol extract of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* was taken & dissolved in 200 µl of pure DMSO & sea water to make 1000 µg/ml concentrated stock solution from this stock solution varying concentration (10µg/ml,20µg/ml,30µg/ml,40µg/ml,50µg/ml) are serially diluted with sea water same procedure was followed for the standard drug 5-flurouracil.

2.7.3 Experimental procedure:

10 live brine shrimp nauplii was taken carefully by micropipette with 2.5 ml simulated sea water then add 2.5 ml plant ethanolic extract solution into each test tube which is serially diluted the process also include control test tube containing 10 live nauplii with 5 ml simulated sea water place under dark area after 24 hours test tube were inspected using a magnifying glass & no. of surviving nauplii was counted & perform a triplicate. Lethality concentration LC₅₀ value was assessed.

Percentage mortality can be calculated by following formula:

$$\% \text{ Moritality} = \frac{\text{no. nauplii taken} - \text{no.of live nauplii}}{\text{no. of nauplii taken}} \times 100$$

3. RESULT AND DISSCUSION:

3.1 Morphological:

TABLE No 1: Morphological Study

Sr.no.	Parameter	Observation
1	Odor	Sweet smell
2	Color	Greenish
3	Taste	Sweet
4	Consistency	Solid – powder

Morphological characteristics includes the macroscopic study related to the color, odor, taste and consistency of the leaves of *Colocasia esculenta*. Study of the preliminary macroscopic characteristics or organoleptic characteristics of the plant powder such as color, odor, taste and consistency are the first step of establishing the identify and purity of the plant.

3.2 Powder characteristics:

TABLE NO 2: POWDER CHARCTERISTICS TESTS

Sr.n o.	Reagent	Observati on	Characterist ics
1	Phloroglucinol + conc.HCL (1:1)	RED	Lignified xylem vessels (V.B)
2	Sudan red III	Red	Cuticle
3	Hydrochloric acid	Crystals gets dissolved	Calcium oxalate
4	Sulphuric acid	Formation of needle shaped crystal of calcium sulphate	Calcium oxalate

Calcium oxalate is a common bio mineral in plants, occurring as crystals of various shapes. It is a vital component of the load-bearing network, powder microscopy of leaves powder of *Colocasia esculenta* shows the presence of lignified cell, mucilage, calcium oxalate crystals. This is used for the standardization of the drug.

3.3 Physicochemical evaluation:

TABLE NO 3: Physicochemical values of leaves of *Colocasia esculenta*

Sr.no	Parameters	Percentage (%)
1	Total ash	5.68%
2	Acid soluble ash	101.66%
3	Water soluble ash	103.75%
4	Water soluble extractive value	4%
5	Alcohol soluble extractive value	14%

Leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* was subjected to the proximate analysis such as total ash value, water soluble ash value, acid insoluble ash value, water soluble extractive value and alcohol soluble extractive value. this proximate analysis helps to identify the adulteration and gives the information about the quality of the sample. Ash value is useful in determination the purity of the sample.

3.4 Phytochemical:

TABLE NO 4: Phytochemical screening of ethanol of *Colocasia esculenta*

Phytoconstituents	Test	Ethanol
Alkaloids	Dragendorff's test	++
	Mayer's test	-
	Hanger's test	++
	Wagner's test	++
Flavonoids	Shinoda's test	--
	Lead acetate test.	++
	Alkaline test	++
	Sulphuric acid test	++
Glycosides	Legal's test	++
	Killer – Killani test	++
	Modified Bontrager's test	+
	Test for saponin glycoside (Foam test)	
Tannis& phenols	Lead acetate test.	-
	Dil. Iodine solution	-
	Dil.HNO ₃	++
	5%fecl ₃	+
Carbohydrates	Molish reagent	-
	Fehling's test	-
	Benedict's test	+

Absent = (-), Present = (+)

The presence of phytochemical constituents of ethanolic extracts of *Colocasia esculenta* such as Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Tannins, Phenol's, Saponins, and Carbohydrates. So, the ethanolic extract is used for the further research.

3.5 Pharmacological evaluation:

TABLE NO 5: Effect of Ethanolic extract of *Colocasia esculenta* on percent mortality using Brine Shrimp Lethality bioassay.

Concentration (µg/ml)	No. of dead nauplii out of 10			Dead nauplii out of 30	Live nauplii out of 30	% mortality Mean ± SEM	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
	T 1	T 2	T 3				
10	5	4	3	12	18	4±0.5773	
20	7	4	4	15	15	5±1.000	
30	8	4	6	18	12	6±1.1547	48.1
40	9	6	7	22	8	7.33±0.8819	
50	10	7	6	23	7	7.66±1.2018	

TABLE NO 6: Effect of 5-Flurouracil (Standard) on *Colocasia esculenta* on percent mortality using Brine Shrimp Lethality bioassay.

Concentration (µg/ml)	No. of dead nauplii out of 10			Dead nauplii out of 30	Live nauplii out of 30	% Mortality Mean ± SEM	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
	T 1	T 2	T 3				
0.5	4	5	5	14	16	4.67±0.3333	
1	5	6	7	18	12	6.00±0.5773	
1.5	6	7	8	21	9	7.00±0.5773	43
2	7	8	9	24	6	8.00±0.5773	
2.5	8	9	10	27	3	9.00±0.5773	

Fig no.1: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Colocasia esculenta* on percent mortality using Brine Shrimp Lethality bioassay

Fig no.2: Effect of standard of *Colocasia esculenta* on percent mortality using Brine Shrimp Lethality bioassay

The brine shrimp lethality bio-assay represents a rapid, inexpensive and simple bioassay for testing plant extract's bio-activity which in most cases correlates reasonably well with cytotoxic. The brine shrimp assay is very useful tool for the isolation of bio-active compounds from plant extract. The significant lethality of brine shrimp due to extracts of *Agave cantula* is an indicative of

the presence of potent cytotoxic components which warrants further investigation.

After enumerating the number of shrimps surviving after 24 hour the percentage inhibition was evaluated. The Lethality concentration (LC₅₀) of the standard, podophyllotoxin was the data 's are represented in the Table No.6.

The results obtained for the bioassay with alcoholic extract of *Colocasia esculenta* was tabulated in Table No. 5, the lethality concentration (LC₅₀) was founded. There was a gradual increase in the percentage inhibition with the increase in concentration of alcoholic extract.

4. CONCLUSION:

The phytoconstituents in *Colocasia esculenta* would be more concentrated in the ethanolic extract, as evidenced by the plant's higher extractive value in ethanol than in water. *Colocasia esculenta*'s ethanolic extract revealed the presence of tannins, glycosides, alkaloids, and carbohydrates. It was discovered that the *Colocasia esculenta* extract contains a significantly higher concentration of phytochemical ingredients, which makes it useful for creating novel formulations. The current study's overall findings point to the anti-cancer properties of *Colocasia esculenta* leaves, however more research is needed to identify the key ingredients causing these properties. The study's findings offered empirical evidence in favor of the traditional medical system's usage of the plant's leaves to cure tumors.

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Conflict of interest

None to declare

Ethics approval

None to declare.

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